

theory^{14,15}. The ratio DT/DQ (0.525) suggests appreciable distortion in the complex.

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Alkali-Metal Complexes : Acid Salt Complexes of Alkali-Metal Salts of 1-Nitroso-2-Naphthol and 8-Hydroxyquinoline with Oxygen Donor Ligands

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WE report the synthesis of some acid salt complexes of alkali cations of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N) and 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ) with oxygen containing ligands e.g. salicylic acid (Sa1A), 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (2H3NA) and acetyl salicylic acid (AcSa1A). The method of preparation was the same as mentioned earlier¹⁻³.

Results and Discussion

All the products are stable in air, sparingly soluble in most polar solvents but decompose in non-polar solvents. These brown/yellow adducts of alkali-metal salts of 1N2N/8HQ and Sa1A, AcSa1A or 2H3NA, when warmed with either benzene or chloroform deposit green/pale yellow powders. Analysis and ir spectrum show that the powders are the 1:1 products of 1N2N/8HQ. These organic solvents leach out Sa1A, AcSa1A and 2H3NA from the brown/yellow adducts and leave behind a 1:1 salt of 1N2N/8HQ, suggesting that 1N2N/8HQ is more strongly bonded to the metal.

The transition or decomposition temperatures of some complexes are much higher than that of the ligands but in a few cases no conclusion can be drawn. The analysis and physical properties are given in Table 1.

It was believed¹ that the *pK* value was the only factor for the synthesis of these acid salt complexes. We, however, find that the secondary ligands which have lower *pK* values than 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline also participate in adducts. Thus it is seen that 1N2N (*pK*=7.7) and 8HQ (*pK*=9.51), inspite of the higher *pK* values compared to Sa1A (*pK*=2.97), AcSa1A and 2H3NA (*pK*=4.5) form more stable salts⁴.

Infrared spectra : Measurements were made in Nujol mulls for all the complexes and ligands between 4000-650 cm^{-1} . The bands occurring in the region 3500-1500 cm^{-1} only are listed in Table 2.

The disappearance of the O-H band of the secondary ligand (or its shift by 100-150 cm^{-1}) and reappearance between 2600-1800 cm^{-1} suggest that there is strong hydrogen bonding ; when the hydrogen bonding is weak, the bands appear above 2500 cm^{-1} and for strong hydrogen bonding, bands occur between 2200 cm^{-1} and 1800 cm^{-1} . Utilising the relationship given by Lord and Merryfield⁵, the hydrogen bonded oxygen-oxygen distance in these complexes have been estimated to lie between 2.5-2.6 Å. These values, however, have only a comparative significance as many factors influence the oxygen-oxygen distance.

None of these acid salt complexes show anomalous and broad absorption bands between 700-1300 cm^{-1} . As such, acid salt structure with very short O...H...O (ca. 2.4 Å) is most improbable.

All the second ligands provide two binding sites for metal ions. The infrared spectra of the complexes suggest strong hydrogen bonding involving the —OH groups in most of the cases and the bands corresponding to the —COOH groups have been found to be metal sensitive.

NOTES

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Melting (m), decomposition (d) or transition (t) temperature	Found%				Calcd.%			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
Li1N2N.Sa1A	Dark brown	215-220°d	63.51	3.81	4.09	—	64.35	3.79	4.42	—
Na1N2N.Sa1A	Dark brown	198-200°d	60.80	2.91	3.88	6.80	61.26	3.60	4.20	6.91
K1N2N.Sa1A	Yellowish green	170°t, 180°d	58.29	3.40	3.88	11.00	58.45	3.44	4.01	11.18
Li8HQ.Sa1A	Canary yellow	117-120°m	65.72	4.00	4.31	—	66.44	4.15	4.84	—
Na8HQ.Sa1A	Yellow	105-110°m	62.60	3.90	4.45	7.50	62.95	3.93	4.59	7.54
K8HQ.Sa1A	Yellow	105-110°m	58.16	3.25	4.81	12.00	59.81	3.74	4.36	12.15
Li1N2N.AcSa1A	Dark brown	235-240°d	63.39	3.88	4.11	—	63.51	3.90	3.90	—
Na1N2N.AcSa1A	Greenish brown	210°d	60.71	3.68	3.51	6.05	60.80	3.73	3.73	6.13
K1N2N.AcSa1A	Greenish brown	190°d	59.21	3.70	3.98	9.65	58.31	3.58	3.58	9.97
Li8HQ.AcSa1A	Pale Yellow	146-150°d	66.30	3.10	4.19	—	65.26	4.23	4.23	—
K8HQ.AcSa1A	Cream	160° mcd	59.51	3.28	3.71	10.65	59.50	3.86	3.86	10.74
Li1N2N.2H3NA	Brown	195-200°d	69.12	3.21	3.42	—	68.66	3.82	3.82	—
Na1N2N.2H3NA	Brown	155-160°d	65.60	3.54	3.53	5.95	65.80	3.66	3.66	6.01
K1N2N.2H3NA	Yellowish green	180°d	62.91	3.72	3.14	9.52	63.16	3.51	3.51	9.77
Li8HQ.2H3NA	Light brown	230-235°d	70.21	4.30	3.81	—	70.80	4.13	4.13	—
Na8HQ.2H3NA	Yellow	150-155°d	67.01	3.56	3.77	6.35	67.61	3.94	3.94	6.48
K8HQ.2H3NA	Yellow	150°d	64.51	3.52	3.71	10.40	64.69	3.77	3.77	10.51

1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol; 8HQ=8-hydroxyquinoline; Sa1A=salicylic acid; AcSa1A=acetyl salicylic acid and 2H3NA=2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid.

TABLE 2—SELECTED ABSORPTION BANDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS (IN cm^{-1})

	O—H/O...H—O		O...H—O/O...H—N				O...H—O		
1N2N		3300br		3055				1640(N=O)	
Sa1A		3240(O—H)					1660(C=O)		1483
Li1N2N.Sa1A		3280					1630	1600	
Na1N2N.Sa1A	3400		2300	1880	1680	1670	1640	1620	
K1N2N.Sa1A	3400	3360	2300br	1920	1690	1675	1650	1615	
8HQ		3440(OH)							1580(C=N)
Li8HQ.Sa1A			3100-3050				1650	1630br	1600 1560
Na8HQ.Sa1A			3100-3050	2500-2400			1645	1625	1595
K8HQ.Sa1A			3100-3000	2500-2450	1800		1635		1600
AcSa1A		3300-3100br		2500-2400	1750	1680	1650sh		1600
Li1N2N.AcSa1A		3270			1890		1640(N=O)		1615 1520
Na1N2N.AcSa1A			3030	2500	1880-60	1660	1650sh	1640	1615 1520
K1N2N.AcSa1A	3420	3350br		2250br	1910	1695	1660br	1645	1615 1520
Li8HQ.AcSa1A		3300		2550-2500			1660		1615 1560
2H3NA		3265				1680sh	1660	1620	1590 1500
Li1N2N.2H3NA		3250						1630	
Na1N2N.2H3NA		3250	3030	2550-2500	1900	1645	1635	1610	1585 1500
K1N2N.2H3NA	3420	3380		2300br	1820br	1658	1650	1630	1580 1500
Li8HQ.2H3NA		3300-3200						1600	1585 1500
Na8HQ.2H3NA				2500	1850-1800			1615	1595 1585 1570
K8HQ.2H3NA			3100-3000	2550-2500	1800			1630	1595 1500

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Studies on the Kinetics of Production of Charge Carriers in $\text{CuCl} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ System*

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PURE cuprous chloride is a white crystalline material having zinc blende lattice but usually has a yellowish greenish appearance as a result of oxidation of cuprous chloride by air. The

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